

Hackathon Post-Survey Template

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This template contains a collection of measures to assess the perception of hackathon participants after an event has ended. The measures included in this template cover **individual aspects** such as a participant's motivation to participate, prior hackathon experience, programming experience, and demographics. They also cover **team aspects** such as a participant's perception of the team composition, the team process, and the team's project. In addition, the template contains measures related to a participant's perception of the **community** that organized the event and the **hackathon** itself.

The measures included in the template are based on previously validated scales. The respective sources are referenced next to each scale. The scales included here have been utilized as part of the data collection for various studies of hackathons that have been published in various venues in the domains of software engineering [1, 3, 8, 9], human-computer interaction [2, 5, 6], and beyond [4, 7, 10].

We do not suggest using all measures contained in this template for each event. In fact, measures are often only suitable for hackathons that focus on specific goals (e.g., programming experience might only be relevant for a programming-related event). Moreover, there are also measures that assess very similar aspects of an event but in a slightly different way (e.g., the participant's overall satisfaction with an event and their intentions to participate in a similar event again in the future). We thus encourage whoever uses this template to create a survey that fits their specific needs. This includes adding scales that might be important for a specific event and removing scales that are not perceived to be relevant. However, when adapting the survey, please make sure to keep the scales intact. Altering them might compromise their integrity. In addition, **we suggest including items that are marked with a hash (#) in every hackathon survey**. We found these helpful for most, if not all, hackathon events.

If you utilize this instrument to study an event, we would appreciate it if you would be willing to share anonymized responses with us. Please contact the main author for further details. This instrument is available on Zenodo and on the Hackathon Planning Kit (<https://hackathon-planning-kit.org/>).

Survey Cover Page

As an attendee of the [HACKATHON_NAME] hackathon, you are invited to complete the following survey. This hackathon is organized by [HACKATHON_ORGANIZERS]. The main purpose of this survey is [SURVEY_PURPOSE].

The questions are mostly multiple choice / agree-disagree and will take approximately [COMPLETION_TIME_IN_MINUTES] minutes to answer. The risks that are associated with this survey are no greater than those ordinarily encountered in daily life. Your decision regarding whether or not to participate in this study will not result in any loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. Your participation in this survey is voluntary, and you may discontinue participation at any time. Your responses will be de-identified and will remain confidential to the study team.

Anonymized responses to this survey might also be shared with a group of researchers at Eindhoven University of Technology.

If you have any further questions about the survey, please contact [ROLE] [HACKATHON_ORGANIZER_NAME] ([HACKATHON_ORGANIZER_EMAIL]).

I am age 18 or older, I have read and understood the above information, and I wish to participate in the research and continue with the survey.

- Yes (continue the survey)
- No (end the survey)

Section 1: Previous Experience and Motivation

The following questions are related to your prior hackathon experience and your motivations to participate in this event.

1. (#) How many hackathons have you participated in the past?
If you cannot recall the exact number, please provide a rough estimate.
- Short Answer (Number)
2. (#) To what extent was your decision to participate in this hackathon motivated by... (scale, [1, 2])

	Not at All	To some extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	Completely
Having fun					
Making something cool / Working on an interesting project idea					
Learning about [PURPOSE]					
[HACKATHON_THEME]					
Meeting new people					
Seeing what others are working on					
Sharing my experience and expertise					
Joining friends that participate					
Dedicated time to get work done					
Win a prize					

3. (#) If your participation is motivated by other than the above reasons, please describe additional motivations below.

- Short Answer (text)

Section 2: Teamwork During this Hackathon

The following questions are related to your perception of the team you were a part of during this hackathon.

1. (#) What was the name of your team / project? (mandatory)
 - Short answer (text or number)
2. (#) How many people were in your team (including yourself)?
 - Short answer (number)

3. (#) Did your team use a code repository? If yes, please provide the URL of that repository below.

- Short answer (URL)

4. (#) Did your team use any other online resources to e.g. create documentation? If yes, please provide the URL of that resource below.

- Short answer (URL)

5. (#) Was there a team leader?

A team leader is someone who provides guidance, instruction, direction and leadership to the team.

- Yes, I was the team leader.
- Yes, someone else was the team leader.
- No, there was no clear leader in the team.

6. (#) How do you estimate your programming experience compared to your team members? ([11])

- Very inexperienced
- Inexperienced
- Comparable
- Experienced
- Very experienced

7. (#) How well did you know your team members? (scale, [12])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I knew my team members well.					
I have collaborated with some of my team members before.					
I have been close to some of my team members before.					

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I have socialized with some of my team members (outside of this hackathon) before.					

Section 3: Teamwork During this Hackathon Continued...

The following questions are related to your perception of the team you were a part of during this hackathon.

1. (#) Would you describe your team process as more... (scale, [1])

	1	2	3	4	5
(1) Inefficient to (5) Efficient					
(1) Uncoordinated to (5) Coordinated					
(1) Unfair to (5) Fair					
(1) Confusing to (5) Easy to understand					

2. (#) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your GOALS as a team. (scale, [1])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I was uncertain of my duties and responsibilities in this team.					
I was unclear about the goals and objectives for my work in this team.					

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I was unsure how my work related to the overall objectives of my team.					

3. (#) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your TEAM. (scale, [1])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Everyone had a chance to express his/her opinion.					
The team members responded to the comments made by others.					
The team members participated very actively during our collaboration.					
Overall, the participation of each member in the team was effective.					

Section 4: Your hackathon project

The following questions are related to your perception of the project you worked on during this hackathon.

1. (#) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your SATISFACTION with your project. (scale, [1])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied with the work completed in my project.					
I am satisfied with the quality of my team's output.					
My ideal outcome coming into my team was achieved.					
My expectations towards my team were met.					

2. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to the USEFULNESS of your project. (scale, [13, 14, 15, 16])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
My project improves my performance during my everyday work.					
My project improves my productivity during my everyday work.					
My project improves my effectiveness during my everyday work.					
Overall, my project will be useful during my everyday work.					

3. Please indicate your FUTURE INTENTIONS related to your hackathon project. (scale, [13, 14, 15, 16])

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I intend to continue working on my hackathon project rather than not continue working on it.					
My intentions are to continue working on my hackathon project rather than any other project.					
If I could, I would like to continue working on my hackathon project as much as possible.					

4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your ABILITY to continue working on your hackathon project. (scale, [13, 16])

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I would be able to continue working on my hackathon project.					
Continuing to work on my hackathon project is entirely under my control.					
I have the resources, knowledge, and ability					

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
to continue working on my project after the hackathon.					

Section 5: Community relationship

The following questions are related to your perception of the community that organized this event.

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your RELATIONSHIP with the community that organized this event. (scale, [17])

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I feel I am part of this community.					
I am interested in what goes on in this community.					
Interacting with other members of this community makes me want to try new things.					
I am willing to spend time to support general activities in this community.					
Through this community I come into contact with new people all the time.					
There are several people in this community that I trust					

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
to help me solve my problems.					
I know someone in this community that I can turn to if I urgently need help.					
There is someone in this community that I can turn to for advice about making important decision.					
The other members of this community would be good job references for me.					
I do not know people in this community well enough to get them to do anything important.					

2. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your PERCEPTION of the community that organized this event. (scale, [18])

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I identify with other members of this community.					
I am like other members of this community.					
This community is an important reflection of who I am.					

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I would like to continue working with this community.					
I dislike being a member of this community.					
I would rather belong to another community.					

Section 6: Hackathon experience

The following questions are related to your perception of this hackathon.

1. (#) How do you feel about your OVERALL EXPERIENCE participating in this hackathon?
(scale, [14, 19])

	1	2	3	4	5
(1) Very dissatisfied to (5) Very satisfied					
(1) Very displeased to (5) Very pleased					
(1) Very frustrated to (5) Very contented					
(1) Absolutely terrible to (5) Absolutely delighted					

2. Do you plan to participate in a similar event in the future?

- Definitely not
- Probably not
- Might or might not
- Probably yes
- Definitely yes

3. (#) What did you like about this hackathon?

- Long answer (text)

4. (#) What would you wish to be different about this hackathon?

- Long answer (text)
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Section 7: Demographics and individual background

The following questions are about your personal background.

1. (#) How old are you currently?

- 18 to 24
- 25 to 34
- 35 to 44
- 45 to 54
- 55 to 64
- 65 to 74
- 75 or older
- Prefer not to say

2. (#) Are you...?

(Can be replaced by a text entry field: "If you feel comfortable, we invite you to share your gender with us.")

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

3. What is the highest level of formal education that you have completed until now?

- High school diploma or GED
- Some college
- Associate and/or bachelor's degree
- Bachelor's degree

- Professional degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Prefer not to say

4. (#) Do you consider yourself a minority? (For example in terms of background, gender, expertise or in another way)

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

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